

Genetic Frequencies of Blood Group from Gene Pool of Third Year and Fourth Year Zoology Students, Dagon University Year 2016

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Abstract

346 Zoology 3rd Year and 4th Year Students were analyzed. The result showed that 150 (34.8 %) students of B Group, 127 (29.2 %) students of O group, 114 (25.6 %) students of A group and 45 (10.4 %) students of AB blood groups. Allelic frequency of I^A (0.20 %), I^B (0.26 %), and i (0.53 %) were calculated. Total of 20 students were Rh negative results. Among them, 15 girls who were Rh negative groups may have hazard at the time of pregnancy during their marriage.

Key word : Allelic frequency, Blood group ABO & Rh, Zoology students, Dagon University

Introduction

The ABO blood group system is the important blood type system in human transfusion. Which is found on platelets epithelium and cells other than erythrocytes. AOB blood types are also present in some other animals, for example rodents and apes such as chimpanzees, bonobos and gorillas (Wikipedia, 2016).

The ABO blood group system was discovered by the Austrian scientist Karl Landsteiner who was awarded the Noble prize in 1930 identified the O, A and B blood types in 1900. Landsteiner originally described the O blood type as type C and in parts of Europe, it is rendered as 'O' zero signifying the lack of A or B antigen. Alfred von Decastello and Adriano Strurli discovered the fourth type, AB in 1902 (Wikipedia, 2016).

There are three basic variants of immuglobulin antigens humans that share a very similar chemical structure but are distinctly different. Red circle shows where there difference in chemical structure in the antigen-binding site of human immuglobulin. The O-type antigen does not have a binding site (Wikipedia, 2016).

In addition to the ABO system, the Rh blood group system can affect transfusion compatibility. An individual is either positive or negative for the Rh factor, this is donated by a + or – after their ABO type. Those with Rh-positive blood can safely receive both Rh-positive and Rh-negative blood. Those with Rh-negative blood should only receive Rh-negative blood. Rh-negative blood is used in emergencies when there is no time to test a person's Rh type. The AB^+ type is referred to as the "universal recipient", as there are anti A or anti-B antibodies in its plasma and can receive both Rh-positive and Rh-negative blood. Similarly, the O-blood type is called the 'universal donor' since its red cells have no A or B antigens and are Rh-negative, no other blood type will reject it (Wikipedia, 2016).

Blood groups are inherited from both parents. The ABO blood types are controlled by a single gene with three types of alleles inferred from classical genetics i , I^A and I^B . the I designation stands for isoagglutinogen another term for antigen (Wikipedia, 2016).

The I^A allele gives blood type A, I^B gives type B, and i gives type O. As that I^A and I^B are dominant over i , only ii people have type O blood. Individuals with $I^A I^A$ or $I^A i$ have type A blood and individuals with $I^B I^B$ or $I^B i$ have the B blood $I^A I^B$ people have both phenotypes,

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because A and B express a special dominance relationship, co-dominance ($I^A = I^B$), which means that type A and B parents can have an AB child. A couple with type A and type B can also have a type O child if they are heterozygous ($I^B i, I^A i$) has a single enzyme that creates both A and B antigens. The resulting red blood cells do not usually express A or B antigen at the same level that would be expected on common group A or B red blood cells, which can help solve the problem of an apparently genetically impossible blood group (Wikipedia, 2016). Thus in the present study was under taken with the following objectives:

- To record the frequency of blood groups of samples student group
- To calculate allelic and genotypic frequencies of blood groups
- To remind the health hazard of students concerning with blood types

Materials and Methods

Sampling area and site

A total of 436 students of third year and fourth years of Zoology Students, Zoology Department, Dagon University of the academic year 2015-2016.

Study period

The study period lasted from July, 2016 to August 2016.

Collection method of blood samples

The blood samples were collected from each student after their consent to participate in this research process. The blood sample collection was performed by using blood lancets and a lancing device, to obtain a drop of blood from a sterilized finger from each individual. Blood samples were taken from finger pricks, and open slide method of testing for ABO blood groups and Rh(D) factor was followed (Bhasin and Chahal, 1996). Three drops of blood sample of each individual separately placed on a clean glass slide. A drop of each of the anti sera (anti sera A, anti sera B and anti sera D) was mixed with each blood drop of the sample. Blood was then mixed thoroughly with the anti sera and rocked gently for 60 sec to observe agglutination. Blood group was determined on the basis of agglutination and recorded as blood group A^+ , B^+ , AB^+ , O^+ or A^- , B^- , AB^- and O^- .

Method of allelic frequency analysis

The allelic frequencies were computed for (I^A , I^B and i) with frequencies equal to p , q and r respectively. The frequencies of the genotypes at equilibrium were computed by the trinomial expansion $(p + q + r)^2 = p^2 (AA) + 2pq (AB) + q^2 (BB) + 2pr (AO) + 2qr (BO) + r^2 (OO)$. The four blood group phenotypes were indicated as $\overline{A}$, $\overline{B}$, $\overline{AB}$ and $\overline{O}$. The frequencies of the blood group phenotypes were calculated as the number of individuals belonging to the phenotypic class divided by the total number for the types. According to Hardy-Weinberg law, formula for the calculation of allelic frequency after (Griffiths, 2008) was as follows:

$$p = 1 - \sqrt{\overline{B + O}} \quad q = 1 - \sqrt{\overline{A + O}} \quad r = \sqrt{\overline{O}}$$

where, p , q , r = Frequency of A, B, O blood groups

$$\text{Gene frequency of (Rh}^-\text{) } d = \sqrt{\overline{d}}$$

where d = proportion of the population in Rh group.

$$\text{Gene frequency of (Rh}^+\text{) } D = 1 - d$$

A. Finger pricking by a lancing device

B. Placing drops of blood sample on glass slide

C. Applying anti sera to blood drops

D. Mixing anti sera with blood for agglutination

Plate 1. Equipment and anti sera utilized for blood sample collection

Results

A total of 436 the third year and fourth year Zoology students were utilized to collect blood samples for this study. They include 119 males and 317 female between 18 and 23 years of age. Among them the maximum number of 150 were recorded of possessing blood group B with a percentage value of 34.8 % followed by 127 individuals possessing blood group O (29.2 %) and 114 individuals with blood group A (25.6 %) while the remaining 45 individuals who were found with blood group AB (10.4 %) was the least preponderant. On the other hand among 119 males and 317 females individuals the blood group B still outnumbered the other blood groups with 43 and 107 individual each, so is most preponderant giving percentages of 36.13 % and 33.75 % respectively. However, in male sex, blood group A is the second most preponderant with 33 recorded individuals giving a percentage of 27.73 % and then blood group O with 31 individuals 26.06 % and the least was 12 individuals with blood group AB 10.08 %. In case of females the blood group O possessing 96 individuals formed the second most important group with a percentage of 30.28 % and after that 81 individuals possessing blood group A giving a percentage of 25.55 % and the least was with 33 individuals having blood group AB giving rise to a percentage of 10.42 % (Table 1).

As the Rh (D) antigen is concerned, a very low percentage of individual was found to be Rh (D) negative in the present study. The result also showed a total of 436 individuals, 95.41 % of the studied population were Rh (D) positive while the rest 4.59 % population were Rh (D) negative. All the twenty (20) individuals who are Rh (D) negative and are represented by five (5) male with 4.20 % and fifteen (15) with a percentage of 4.73 %. In case of allele Rh (D) and Rh(d), the frequency of allele D was for higher than allele d with the recorded values of 0.80 and 0.20 respectively (Table 2).

Allele (gene) frequency, I^A showed a frequency of 0.20 while I^B showed a frequency of 0.26 while the highest was of i with a recorded frequency of 0.54. Genotypic frequency ($p^2 + 2pr$) of blood group A was 0.256, ($q^2 + 2qr$) of blood group B was 0.348, ($2pq$) of blood group AB was 0.104 and (r^2) of blood group O was 0.292 respectively (Table 3).

A. Blood Group A⁺

B. Blood Group A⁻

C. Blood Group B⁺

D. Blood Group B⁻

E. Blood Group AB⁺

F. Blood Group AB⁻

G. Blood Group O⁺

H. Blood Group O⁻

Plate 2. Distribution of blood group ABO among third year and fourth year Zoology students

Table 1. Distribution of the ABO blood groups among Third and Fourth year Zoology students

Blood groups	Male		Female		Total	
	No	%	No	%	No	%
A	33	27.73	81	25.55	114	25.6
B	43	36.13	107	33.75	150	34.8
AB	12	10.08	33	10.42	45	10.4
O	31	26.06	96	30.28	127	29.2
Total	119	100	317	100	436	100

Table 2. Distribution of the Rh (D) blood groups and allele frequencies among third and fourth year Zoology students

Phenotype	Number	Allele frequency	Percentage
Rh D(+) positive	416 (114 M + 302 F)	0.80	95.41
Rh D(-) negative	20 (5 M +15 F)	0.20	4.59
Total	436	1.00	100.00

Fig 1. Percentage of the ABO and Rh(D) blood group in the third year and fourth year Zoology Students

Table 3. Distribution of the ABO blood groups and allele frequencies among third and fourth year Zoology students

Phenotype	Number	Genotype	Allele (gene) frequency	Genotypic frequency	Percentage
A	114	$I^A I^A$	$I^A = 0.20$	P^2	25.6
		$I^A i$		$2pr$	
B	150	$I^B I^B$	$I^B = 0.26$	q^2	34.8
		$I^B i$		$2qr$	
AB	45	$I^A I^B$		$2pq = 0.104$	10.4
O	127	ii	$i = 0.54$	$r^2 = 0.292$	29.2

Fig 2. Allele frequency of AOB and RhD blood group among third year and fourth year Zoology students

Table 4. Comparison of frequency percentage of ABO and Rh (D) blood group in Zoology students

Population	A	B	AB	O	Rh ⁺ (D)	Rh ⁻ (D)	Data source
First Year	21.21	34.71	7.28	36.80	98.75	1.25	Dr. Moe Pa Pa Naing 2016
Second Year	25.75	35.07	8.58	30.60	96.65	3.35	Dr. Aye Aye Min, 2016
Present Study	25.6	34.8	10.4	29.2	95.41	4.59	

Table 5. Comparison of frequency percentage of ABO Rhesus blood group in different countries of the world

Population	A	B	AB	O	Rh positive	Rh negative
Britain	42.0	8.0	3.0	47.0	83.0	17.0
USA	41.0	9.0	4.0	46.0	85.0	15.0
Nigeria	21.60	21.40	2.80	54.20	95.20	4.80
New Guinea	22.50	23.70	4.70	48.90	95.90	4.10
Saudi Arabia	24.0	17.0	4.0	52.0	93.0	7.0
Pakistan	22.40	32.40	8.40	30.50	93.0	7.0
Nepal	34.0	29.0	4.0	32.50	96.70	3.30
Myanmar	24.18	35.86	8.75	32.2	96.63	3.37

Discussion and Conclusion

The study of distribution of blood groups is important as it plays a vital role in blood transfusion, organ-transplantation, genetics research, human evolution, forensic pathology and some groups have shown associations with diseases like duodenal ulcer, diabetes mellitus, urinary tract infection and Rh and ABO incompatibilities of newborn.

In the present study, the results of this study were compared with other studies carried out in different Zoology students groups. In first year students, blood group O was commonest followed by B, A and AB, which is different from the present study. In second year student, blood group B was commonest followed by O, A and AB. The present study showed commonest blood group B followed by O, A and AB.

Prakash *et al.*; (2013) reported that blood group B is very common in population of Asia descent, but rare in population of western European descent. In the present study results are in agreement above author with these mentions because Myanmar students are also of Asian descent.

Outside Myanmar, studies were carried out in different countries of the world like Britain, USA, Nigeria, New Guinea, Saudi Arabia, Pakistan and Nepal. Except in Pakistan and Nepal there were increased frequency of O blood group in these countries. In Pakistan, the commonest blood group B followed by O, A and AB. The same prevalence was found in present study i.e. B was most frequent than O, followed by A and AB.

The incidence of Rhesus (D) positive blood group different countries of the world vary from 83.0 to 96.70 and 3.30 to 17.0 were Rh negative. The present study results are within this range.

If the both parents have Rh-positive or Rh-negative genes, all children conceived by the couple will be Rh-positive or Rh-negative. The Rh negative gene is recessive while the Rh positive gene is dominant. This means that there is a greater than or equal to 50 percent chance that an Rh negative mother will conceive and Rh positive baby if the father is Rh positive. Hemolytic disease of the newborn (HDN) or Rh disease occurs if there is Rh incompatibility between a mother and her unborn child. In severe cases of HDN, the fetus may die without medical treatment, or may have low hemoglobin (anemia), toxins in the blood (jaundice) and brain damage. A woman who is Rh-positive will not be affected by having a baby with an Rh-negative man (Anonymous, 2001).

According to the data, the highest number of Rh⁻ 13 (54.16 %) occurred among females in fourth year, followed by 5 (20.83 %) females in first year and 4 (16.70 %) females in second year. The lowest number of 2 (8.34 %) found among of females in third year students were Rh negative. They need treatment for take baby with Rh positive husband.

In the present study, 4 females were O⁻ blood group, they were Universal Donor because O⁻ blood type lack of antigen A, B and D, so they can give blood to any blood type but they can accept only O⁻ blood transfusion. Hence, they must be great careful of they need blood transfusion. Among AB⁺ blood group 39 individuals (10 males and 29 females) were AB⁺ blood group, they were Universal recipient, because this type AB⁺ blood present antigen A, B and D, so, they can receive from any blood type but they can give to only AB⁺ blood. So, they have a good chance for need blood transfusion.

The O blood group is significantly high in present study and comparatively low AB blood group. Every transfusion centre should have a record of frequency of blood group system in their population. It helps in inventory management. Knowledge of blood group distribution is also important for clinical studies, for reliable geographical information and for forensic studies in the population.

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